

Supporting Information for:

Undescribed Amaryllidaceae Alkaloids from *Zephyranthes citrina* and their Cytotoxicity

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HRESIMS spectrum of zephycitrine (1)

2020 05 31 LC 6-50 A 1159 (2.043) Cm (1159:1168-(1139:1153+1204:1235))

1: TOF MS ES+
2.92e5

¹H NMR spectrum (500 MHz) of zephycitrine (1) in CDCl₃

ZC-5-6-3_H

¹³C NMR spectrum (125.7 MHz) of zephycitrine (1) in CDCl₃

ZC-5-6-3_C

HSQC spectrum of zephycitrine (1) in CDCl₃

COSY spectrum of zephycitrine (1) in CDCl₃

H2BC spectrum of zephycitrine (1) in CDCl₃

HMBC spectrum of zephycitrine (1) in CDCl₃

NOESY spectrum of zephycitrine (1) in CDCl₃

Table S1. Comparison of ^1H and ^{13}C NMR chemical shifts (CDCl_3) and optical rotation of zephycitrine (**1**) and haemanthamine (**12**)¹

No.	δ_{C} , type	1 δ_{H} , mult. (<i>J</i> in Hz)	δ_{C} , type	12 δ_{H} , mult. (<i>J</i> in Hz)
1	126.9, CH	6.52, d, overlap (10.0)	127.3, CH	6.43, d (10.2)
2	132.4, CH	6.41, dd (10.0, 4.9)	132.4, CH	6.36, dd (10.2, 4.7)
3	72.7, CH	3.91–3.86, m, overlap	72.7, CH	3.86, ddd (4.7, 4.0, 1.8)
4	28.1, CH ₂	2.22–2.03, m	28.2, CH ₂	2.11, ddd (13.8, 5.4, 1.8) 2.06–1.97, m
4a	62.9, CH	3.48–3.41, m	62.6, CH	3.43–3.30, m
6	60.9, CH ₂	4.42, d (16.5) 3.79, d (16.5)	61.3, CH ₂	4.32, d (17.1) 3.69, d (17.1)
6a	125.2, C		126.7, C	
7	109.7, CH	6.52, s, overlap	106.8, CH	6.47, s
8	148.0, C		146.4, C	
9	147.9, C		146.1, C	
10	106.3, CH	6.84, s	103.3, CH	6.82, s
10a	133.8, C		135.3, C	
10b	49.9, C		50.0, C	
11	80.0, CH	4.06–4.01, m	80.1, CH	3.98, dd (6.7, 3.3)
12	63.3, CH ₂	3.48–3.41, m 3.40–3.35, m	63.5, CH ₂	3.43–3.30, m 3.25 dd, (14.1, 3.3)
3-OCH ₃	56.7, CH ₃	3.38, s, overlap	56.5, CH ₃	3.36, s
8-OCH ₃	55.9, CH ₃	3.83, s	-	-
9-OCH ₃	56.1, CH ₃	3.88, s, overlap	-	-
-OCH ₂ O-	-	-	100.8, CH ₂	5.89, bs; 5.88, bs
$[\alpha]_{\text{D}}$		+46 ° (c 0.20, CHCl ₃ , 23 °C)		+41 ° (c 0.62, CHCl ₃ , 24 °C)

HRESIMS spectrum of 6-oxonarcissidine (2)

2024 04 26 6oN C 1160 (2.025) Cm (1146:1177-(1200:1351+988:1132))

1: TOF MS ES+
8.16e5

¹H NMR spectrum (500 MHz) of 6-oxonarcissidine (2) in CDCl₃

AC-3-1_H

¹³C NMR spectrum (125.7 MHz) of 6-oxonarcissidine (2) in CDCl₃

AC-3-1_Cn

HSQC spectrum of 6-oxonarcissidine (2) in CDCl₃

COSY spectrum of 6-oxonarcissidine (2) in CDCl₃

H2BC spectrum of 6-oxonarcissidine (2) in CDCl₃

HMBC spectrum of 6-oxonarcissidine (2) in CDCl₃

NOESY spectrum of 6-oxonarcissidine (2) in CDCl₃

UV spectrum of 6-oxonarcissidine (2) in MeOH

Table S2. Comparison of ^1H and ^{13}C NMR chemical shifts (CDCl_3) and optical rotation of 6-oxonarcissidine (**2**), 1-*O*-acetyl-3-*O*-methyl-6-oxonarcissidine (**2a**), and narcissidine (**6**)

No.	δ_{C}	2 δ_{H} , mult (<i>J</i> in Hz)	δ_{C}	2a² δ_{H} , mult (<i>J</i> in Hz)	δ_{C}	6 δ_{H} , mult (<i>J</i> in Hz)
1	67.6	4.78, bs	66.8	5.78, br t (2.7)	68.1	4.70–4.65, m
2	80.6	3.88, t (2.1)	79.1	3.77, dd (2.9, 2.0)	80.6	3.80, dd (3.2, 2.4)
3	67.9	4.72, bs	75.8	4.06, br d (1.9)	69.2	4.70–4.65, m
3a	138.5		136.1		140.8	
3a'	59.4	4.85, d (13.4)	60.1	4.72, m	62.5	3.86–3.82, m, overlap
4	122.9	5.95–5.92, m	125.4	5.97, q (1.8)	121.4	5.59–5.57, m
5	52.5	4.67, ddd (16.2, 4.4, 2.1) 4.41–4.36, m	52.6	4.68, ddd (16.1, 5.1, 2.0) 4.40, ddd (16.0, 3.2, 1.6)	62.9	4.07–4.04, m, overlap 3.58, ddd (14.5, 5.7, 2.0), overlap
7	162.5		162.6		54.6	4.07, d (13.0) 3.56, d (13.0)
7a	124.9		130.8		127.4	
8	111.6	7.61, s	111.4	7.57, s	110.6	6.69, s
9	148.0		148.0		147.1	
10	151.9		151.9		148.4	
11	105.6	6.81, s	105.7	6.58, s	107.9	6.90, s
11a	131.3		124.6		129.7	
11b	43.2	3.22–3.17, m	41.6	3.30, ddd (12.8, 2.5, 0.9)	41.8	2.71, dd (11.1, 1.4)
2-OCH ₃	58.4	3.49, s	58.9	3.51, s	58.2	3.45, s
3-OCH ₃	-	-	56.5	3.27, s	-	-
9-OCH ₃	56.2	3.95, s	56.2	3.93, s	56.1	3.83, s, overlap
10-OCH ₃	56.2	3.97, s	56.2	3.86, s	56.0	3.88, s
OCOCH ₃	-	-	21.1	2.01	-	-
OCOCH ₃	-	-	171.1		-	-
$[\alpha]_{\text{D}}$		-84° (<i>c</i> 0.10, MeOH, 23 °C)		-123° (<i>c</i> 0.26, CHCl ₃ , 22 °C)		-56° (<i>c</i> 0.10, MeOH, 23 °C)

HRESIMS spectrum of 6-O-ethylzephyranine F (3)

2024 04 09 Sample 6078 10n7 FINAL BEH B 2766 (4.755) Cm (2752:2769-(2809:2911+2642:2731))

1: TOF MS ES+
1.87e6

¹H NMR spectrum (500 MHz) of 6-O-ethylzephyranine F (3) in CDCl₃

¹³C NMR spectrum (125.7 MHz) of 6-O-ethylzephyranine F (3) in CDCl₃

HSQC spectrum of 6-*O*-ethylzephyranine F (3) in CDCl₃

COSY spectrum of 6-*O*-ethylzephyranine F (3) in CDCl₃

H2BC spectrum of 6-*O*-ethylzephyranine F (3) in CDCl₃

HMBC spectrum of 6-*O*-ethylzephyranine F (3) in CDCl₃

NOESY spectrum of 6-*O*-ethylzephyranine F (3) in CDCl₃

UV spectrum of 6-*O*-ethylzephyranine F (3) in MeOH

HRESIMS spectrum of 6-O-ethylzephyranine E (4)

2020 05 31 LC 6-79 A 1415 (2.488) Cm (1407:1420-(1206:1301+1493:1577))

1: TOF MS ES+
8.69e6

¹H NMR spectrum (500 MHz) of 6-O-ethylzephyranine E (4) in CDCl₃

ZC-F3-5_Hn

¹³C NMR spectrum (125.7 MHz) of 6-O-ethylzephyranine E (4) in CDCl₃

ZC-F3-5_Ca

HSQC spectrum of 6-*O*-ethylzephyranine E (4) in CDCl₃

COSY spectrum of 6-*O*-ethylzephyranine E (4) in CDCl₃

H2BC spectrum of 6-*O*-ethylzephyranine E (4) in CDCl₃

HMBC spectrum of 6-*O*-ethylzephyranine E (4) in CDCl₃

NOESY spectrum of 6-*O*-ethylzephyranine E (4) in CDCl₃

UV spectrum of 6-*O*-ethylzephyranine E (4) in MeOH

ECD spectra of 6-*O*-ethylzephyranine E (4), zephyranine C (8), zephyranine E (9), and zephyranine F (10) in MeOH

Different spectral ranges (200–400 nm and 220–400 nm) showing the visual difference.

6-*O*-ethylzephyranine E (4) [200–400 nm]

ECD (c 0.1 mg/ml, MeOH)

$$\Delta\varepsilon_{202} = +20.29 \quad [\theta]_{202} = +66916$$

$$\Delta\varepsilon_{242} = -2.60 \quad [\theta]_{242} = -8574$$

$$\Delta\varepsilon_{276} = -1.93 \quad [\theta]_{276} = -6365$$

6-*O*-ethylzephyranine E (4) [220–400 nm]

ECD (c 0.1 mg/ml, MeOH)

$$\Delta\varepsilon_{241} = -1.94 \quad [\theta]_{241} = -6398$$

$$\Delta\varepsilon_{277} = -1.76 \quad [\theta]_{277} = -5804$$

zephyranine E (9) [200–400 nm]

ECD (c 0.1 mg/ml, MeOH)

$$\Delta\varepsilon_{200} = +17.29 \quad [\theta]_{200} = +57037$$

$$\Delta\varepsilon_{237} = -2.81 \quad [\theta]_{237} = -9256$$

$$\Delta\varepsilon_{283} = -1.32 \quad [\theta]_{283} = -4340$$

zephyranine E (9) [220–400 nm]

ECD (c 0.1 mg/ml, MeOH)

$$\Delta\varepsilon_{237} = -3.64 \quad [\theta]_{237} = -12001$$

$$\Delta\varepsilon_{283} = -1.58 \quad [\theta]_{283} = -5202$$

zephyranine F (10) [200–400 nm]

ECD (c 0.1 mg/ml, MeOH)

$$\Delta\epsilon_{200} = +24.37 \quad [\theta]_{200} = +80373$$

$$\Delta\epsilon_{244} = -0.53 \quad [\theta]_{244} = -1743$$

$$\Delta\epsilon_{281} = -0.73 \quad [\theta]_{281} = -2413$$

zephyranine F (10) [220–400 nm]

ECD (c 0.1 mg/ml, MeOH)

$$\Delta\epsilon_{244} = -0.83 \quad [\theta]_{244} = -2748$$

$$\Delta\epsilon_{281} = -0.85 \quad [\theta]_{281} = -2815$$

zephyranine C (8) [200–400 nm]

ECD (c 0.1 mg/ml, MeOH)

$$\Delta\epsilon_{200} = +16.91 \quad [\theta]_{200} = +55752$$

$$\Delta\epsilon_{236} = -2.25 \quad [\theta]_{236} = -7415$$

$$\Delta\epsilon_{279} = -0.87 \quad [\theta]_{279} = -2868$$

zephyranine C (8) [220–400 nm]

ECD (c 0.1 mg/ml, MeOH)

$$\Delta\epsilon_{237} = -2.72 \quad [\theta]_{237} = -8911$$

$$\Delta\epsilon_{280} = -1.12 \quad [\theta]_{280} = -3692$$

HRESIMS spectrum of eugenie (5)

2020 05 31 LC 6-43 A 1302 (2.291) Cm (1294:1309-(1193:1250+1366:1418))

1: TOF MS ES+
8.54e6

¹H NMR spectrum (500 MHz) of eugenie (5) in CD₃OD

ZC-15-3-3-3_H

¹³C NMR spectrum (125.7 MHz) of eugenie (5) in CD₃OD

ZC-15-3-3-3_C

HSQC spectrum of eugenine (5) in CD₃OD

COSY spectrum of eugenine (5) in CD₃OD

H2BC spectrum of eugenine (5) in CD₃OD

HMBC spectrum of eugenine (5) in CD₃OD

NOESY spectrum of eugenine (5) in CD₃OD

Experiment with eugenine (5) and Pirkel's reagent in CDCl₃ (lower ¹H NMR spectrum after reagent addition)

UV spectrum of eugenine (5) in MeOH

HRESIMS spectrum of narcissidine (6)

2024 04 25 Sample 6036 FINAL A 1004 (1.759) Cm (998:1025-(1040:1067+968:989))

1: TOF MS ES+
5.92e5

¹H NMR spectrum (500 MHz) of narcissidine (6) in CDCl₃

¹³C NMR spectrum (125.7 MHz) of narcissidine (6) in CDCl₃

HSQC spectrum of narcissidine (6) in CDCl₃

¹H NMR spectrum (500 MHz) of narcissidine (6) in CD₃OD

¹³C NMR spectrum (125.7 MHz) of narcissidine (6) in CD₃OD

HSQC spectrum of narcissidine (6) in CD₃OD

COSY spectrum of narcissidine (6) in CD₃OD

H2BC spectrum of narcissidine (6) in CD₃OD

HMBC spectrum of narcissidine (6) in CD₃OD

NOESY spectrum of narcissidine (6) in CD₃OD

UV spectrum of narcissidine (6) in MeOH

ECD spectrum of narcissidine (6) in MeOH

ECD (c 0.1 mg/ml, MeOH) [220–400 nm]

$$\Delta\varepsilon_{231} = -8.92 \quad [\theta]_{231} = -29418$$

ECD (c 0.1 mg/ml, MeOH) [200–400 nm]

$$\Delta\varepsilon_{200} = +17.80 \quad [\theta]_{200} = +58702$$

$$\Delta\varepsilon_{231} = -12.35 \quad [\theta]_{231} = -40730$$

Table S3. Narcissidine: A comparison of NMR data measured in CD₃OD, CDCl₃, and those found in literature

No.	6^a		6^b		6^{b 3}	6^{b 4}	
	δ_C	δ_H	δ_C	δ_H	δ_H	δ_C	δ_H
1	69.2	4.79–4.73, m	68.1	4.70–4.65, m	4.66, m	67.9	4.70, m
2	82.8	3.72, dd (3.2, 2.6)	80.6	3.80, dd (3.2, 2.4)	4.18–3.36, m	80.0	3.81, t (3.0)
3	69.1	4.62, dd (2.6, 1.3)	69.2	4.70–4.65, m	4.66, m	68.9	4.69, d (3.0)
3a	141.6		140.8				
3a'	63.9	4.00–3.95, m	62.5	3.86–3.82, m ^c	4.18–3.36, m	62.0	3.87, m
4	122.9	5.75–5.73, m	121.4	5.59–5.57, m	5.56, m	120.9	5.61, m
5	63.0	4.05–4.00, m 3.58, ddd (14.2, 5.3, 2.1)	62.9	4.07–4.04, m ^c 3.58, ddd (14.5, 5.7, 2.0) ^c	4.18–3.36, m	62.1	4.07, dt (14.5, 2.0) 3.60, ddd (14.5, 5.5, 2.0)
7	55.6	4.07, d (12.9) 3.62, d (12.9)	54.6	4.07, d (13.0) 3.56, d (13.0)	4.09, d (13.0) 3.54, d (13.0)	54.0	4.10, d (13.0) 3.59, d (13.0)
7a	130.0		127.4				
8	112.5	6.88, s	110.6	6.69, s	6.68, s	110.2	6.70, s
9	148.7		147.1				
10	149.7		148.4				
11	109.8	7.00, s	107.9	6.90, s	6.88, s	107.3	6.90, s
11a	131.8		129.7				
11b	42.1	2.83, ddd (11.2, 1.8, 0.8)	41.8	2.71, dd (11.1, 1.4)	2.70, d (11.0)	41.2	2.74, dd (11.0, 2.0)
2-OCH ₃	58.3	3.46, s	58.2	3.45, s	3.44, s	57.6	3.46, s
9-OCH ₃	56.7	3.82, s	56.1	3.83, s ^c	3.82, s	55.6	3.84, s
10-OCH ₃	56.7	3.86, s	56.0	3.88, s	3.86, s	55.6	3.89, s
[α] _D			-56° (c 0.10, MeOH, 23 °C)		-23° (c 0.58, CHCl ₃ , 22 °C)		-

^a CD₃OD, ^b CDCl₃, ^c overlapped

Data summary for compounds structurally related to 3, 4, 9, and 10

In the beginning, hippeastidine, which could be considered as the parent molecule of **10**, was first described in 1978 by Pacheco and co-workers (mp, IR, UV, low-resolution NMR, MS, $[\alpha]$) when working with *Hippeastrum ananuca* Phil. (currently accepted as *Rhodophiala ananuca* (Phil.) Traub).⁵ Later, its X-ray analysis was published.⁶ Long after that, in 2013, a paper reported the isolation of hippeastidine from *Zephyranthes robusta* Baker (currently recognized as *Habranthus robustus* Herb.) with MS, NMR, and optical rotation data.⁷ However, the optical rotation was given as $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{25} +330$ (c 0.1, CHCl_3), which was quite different from the rotation that reported by Pacheco ($[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{25} -6.9$ (c 2.3, CHCl_3)). In the following year, de Andrade and co-workers described the isolation of aulicine, whose structure was elucidated by X-ray and NMR, among other techniques, resulting in the same structure as already described for hippeastidine in the above mentioned articles.⁸ The justification for giving the molecule a new name was based on inconclusive literature data. When comparing everything known, the only article that deviates is the one from Kulhánková.⁷ Not only the optical rotation, but also the NMR chemical shifts differ. In general, the data published in 1978 and 2014 seem like a match. Another paper reporting hippeastidine derivatives contributed to this confusion when compounds 6-hydroxyhippeastidine and 10-deoxy-6-hydroxyhippeastidine were published in 2014.⁹ The relative configuration was established from NMR data. Interestingly, the authors described the impossibility of registering any Cotton effect in CD analysis and optical rotation was not measured. Hence, we found a solution for this. We noticed a significant visual difference when the samples were measured within the 200–400 nm and 220–400 nm ranges (see S23–S24). The most distinct maximum is usually between 200–210 nm, which is not a diagnostic maximum, and what is worse, it reduces the resolution of the other maxima, which are analytically valid. So, the spectrum may appear to have no Cotton effect. Valid maxima of Amaryllidaceae alkaloids of this type are found in the region of 240 nm and 280 nm. Thus, we

recommend analysis on the 220–400 nm scale to avoid false negative results. All the facts are summarized in **Figure S1**.

not isolated in our study, but named as hippeastidine		
<p>Pacheco et al., 1978 <u>Watson et al., 1982</u> NMR, IR, UV, MS, m.p. [α]_D -6.9 (c 2.3, CHCl₃) X-ray hippeastidine</p>	<p><u>de Andrade et al., 2014</u> NMR, MS, IR, UV [α]_D -2.3 (c 0.4, CHCl₃) CD [Θ]₂₀$_{\lambda}$: [Θ]₂₅₅ +1043, [Θ]₂₇₉ -768 X-ray aulicine</p>	<div style="text-align: center;"> </div> <p><u>Kulhánková et al., 2013</u> NMR, MS, m.p. [α]_D +330 (c 0.1, CHCl₃) configuration not discussed but given hippeastidine</p>
<div style="text-align: center;"> </div> <p><u>Zhan et al., 2023</u> NMR, MS, CD - calculated and experimental, UV, IR (9) zephyranine E R=H [α]_D²⁵ +23 (c 0.8, CH₃OH) CD_{MeOH} [Θ]_{λ}: [Θ]₂₀₈ +15368, [Θ]₂₃₃ -6530, [Θ]₂₈₁ -3034 Our study: [α]_D²³ +67 (c 0.2, CHCl₃) CD_{MeOH} [Θ]_{λ}: [Θ]₂₃₇ -12001, [Θ]₂₈₃ -5202</p>	<p>* mixture of 6-epimers <i>dr</i> 75:25 (6S in excess)</p>	
<div style="text-align: center;"> </div> <p><u>Our study</u> (3) 6-O-ethylzephyranine F R=OH [α]_D²⁵ +44 (c 0.1, CH₃OH)</p>	<p>(10) zephyranine F R=OH [α]_D²⁵ +21 (c 2.3, CH₃OH) CD_{MeOH} [Θ]_{λ}: [Θ]₂₁₁ +19821, [Θ]₂₃₃ -3660, [Θ]₂₈₀ -1682 Our study: [α]_D²³ +61 (c 0.2, CHCl₃) CD_{MeOH} [Θ]_{λ}: [Θ]₂₄₄ -2748, [Θ]₂₈₁ -2815</p>	<p>* only 6S-epimer</p>
<p>(4) 6-O-ethylzephyranine E R=H [α]_D²⁵ +47 (c 0.2, CH₃OH) CD_{MeOH} [Θ]_{λ}: [Θ]₂₄₁ -6398, [Θ]₂₇₇ -5804</p>		

Figure S1. Data summary for compounds structurally related to **3**, **4**, **9**, and **10**. Stereochemistry of compounds adopted from cited articles.⁵⁻¹⁰

Table S4. Screening of compounds **1–8** for their cholinesterase inhibition

compd	IC₅₀ hAChE	IC₅₀ hBChE
	[μM]	[μM]
1	> 100	> 100
2	> 100	> 100
3	> 100	> 100
4	> 100	> 100
5	> 100	> 100
6	> 100	> 100
7	> 100	> 100
8	> 100	> 100
galanthamine*	1.72 $\pm$ 0.12	42.3 $\pm$ 1.3
huperzine A*	0.033 $\pm$ 0.001	> 100
eserine*	0.063 $\pm$ 0.005	0.13 $\pm$ 0.01

* a positive control

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